

Effect of Nanostructured Binary Metal Sulfide (CoS) on its Magnetic and electrochemical behavior for Supercapacitance Applications

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Abstract

Metal sulfides are of great interest for future electrode materials in supercapacitor applications owing to their superior electrochemical activity and excellent electrical conductivity. With this scope, a binary transition metal sulfide (CoS) is prepared via template assisted one-step hydrothermal synthesis. Hexagonal phase of CoS with the space group of $P6_3/mmc$ (194) is confirmed by X-Ray diffraction analysis. The morphological features are visualized using HRSEM results that show nanoflower shaped morphology which agglomerated to form a cluster. The magnetic behavior of the prepared sample was measured using vibrating sample magnetometer which revealed clear hysteresis loop (M-H loop) with paramagnetic nature upto 125 K. At low temperature 2 K and 10 K, the paramagnetic nature gets transformed to ferromagnetic behavior which is further evidenced with the M-T curve. The interfacial charge transport kinetics was examined by EIS-Nyquist plot by employing the prepared CoS as active electrode material. The supercapacitive performances were tested in three electrode system and the estimated specific capacitance for 1A/g is 348 F/g.

Keywords: Binary metal sulfide; CoS; Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy; Supercapacitance.

Fig: HRSEM image of CoS and temperature dependent M-H curve